

Experimental investigation of NO_x emissions during oxyfuel combustion of natural gas-hydrogen blends with the addition of false air

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- Oxyfuel combustion to reduce fuel consumption, especially for expensive fuels like hydrogen
- How to measure NO_x in (hydrogen-)oxyfuel combustion?
- How to quantify NO_x in (hydrogen-)oxyfuel combustion?
- How to avoid NO_x in oxyfuel?

To keep in mind

Characteristic value (oxyfuel)	NG	H ₂
Adiabatic Flame Temperature in K	3048	3073
Calorific Value in kWh/m ³	10.68	3.00
Min. dry off-gas volume in m ³ /m ³	1.24	0.03

NO-formation rate for thermal NO (Zeldovich)

$$\frac{d(NO)}{dt} = 2k_1(N_2)(O)$$

Quantification of NO_x Emissions

NO_x in mg/m³_{dry}

- Most common
- Does not take into account different dry off-gas volumes for different fuel gases

NO_x in mg/kWh

- Fair comparison between fuels for constant power
- Does not consider false air if $x_{O_2 false air} \neq x_{O_2 oxidizer}$

NO_x in kg/h or kg/t

- Fair comparison between fuels
- Accurate volume flow measurement needed

NO_x in mg/kWh new

- Considers false air
- Does not consider that different fuel gases might change the power needed for a process
- In some cases very unstable

Quantification of NO_x Emissions

NO_x in mg/kWh

- Does not consider false air if
 $x_{O_2 \text{ false air}} \neq x_{O_2 \text{ oxidizer}}$

$$Q_{NO_x} \left[\frac{mg}{kWh} \right] = Q_{NO_x, dry} [ppmv_{dry}] \cdot \rho_{NO_2} \cdot \left(\frac{x_{O_2, Ox}}{x_{O_2, Ox} - y_{O_2, dry, M}} \right) \cdot \frac{v_{og, dry, min}}{H_i}$$

NO_x in mg/kWh new

- Considers false air

$$Q_{NO_x} \left[\frac{mg}{kWh} \right] = Q_{NO_x, dry} [ppmv_{dry}] \cdot \rho_{NO_2} \cdot \left(\frac{x_{O_2, dry, \lambda} - x_{O_2 fa}}{y_{O_2, dry, M} - x_{O_2 fa}} \right) \cdot \frac{v_{og, dry, \lambda}}{H_i}$$

Quantification of NO_x Emissions

Example Calculation

- Based on 2.5 t/d oxyfuel glass melting furnace in Aachen with 150 kW burner power
- NO_x limit value for mini-melter: 0.2 kg/h

Case 1	Natural gas	No false air
Case 2	Hydrogen	No false air
Case 3	Natural gas	10% false air
Case 4	Hydrogen	10% false air

Quantification of NO_x Emissions

Example Calculation

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Test Bench and Experimental Procedure

Overview

- Fuel and Oxidizer flexible Burner with three Outlets (Air, Oxygen, Fuel) operated at 17 kW
- Heat up with selected gas composition with oxyfuel for at least 3 hours
- Parameter study with variation of furnace temperature, fuel gas and false air addition

Test Bench and Experimental Procedure

Cooling and Dilution Unit

- Dilution of dry off-gas for comparable concentrations in the dry off-gas for different fuel gases
- Off-gas is dried before dilution
- Measurements with and without dilution

Results

- For NO_x in $\text{mg}/\text{m}^3_{\text{dry}}$ emissions rise with hydrogen content in fuel
- For both NO_x in mg/kWh emissions decrease with hydrogen content in fuel
- NO_x in mg/kWh with new method show higher values than calculations with the established equation

Results

- Decrease in nitrogen volume flow to furnace with increasing hydrogen content

$$Q_{NOx} \left[\frac{mg}{kWh} \right] = Q_{NOx,dry} [ppmv_{dry}] \cdot \rho_{NO2} \cdot \left(\frac{x_{O2,dry,\lambda} - x_{O2fa}}{y_{O2,dry,M} - x_{O2fa}} \right) \cdot \frac{v_{og,dry,\lambda}}{H_i}$$

Main effects plots

Temperature, Dilution, False Air

- Strong dependency between false air addition and NO_x emissions
- Dilution leads to slightly higher NO_x emissions
- No influence of furnace temperature on NO_x emissions

Main effects plots

Fuel gas composition

- For NO_x in mg/m^3 increase in emissions with hydrogen content in fuel
- Both NO_x in mg/kWh show a decrease in emissions
- Local maximum and minima with new calculation method → more unstable

Conclusion and Outlook

- Quantification of NO_x emissions should be done very carefully for oxyfuel combustion, especially for comparison between different fuels
- Dilution unit works well for oxyfuel, but shows weakness for false air addition
- Fuel gas composition and false air addition have biggest influence on NO_x emissions
- In the future, different measurement systems and dilution gases will be compared

Your contact

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NO_x emissions per m³_{dry}

$$Q_{NO_x,dry,ref} \left[\frac{mg}{m^3_{dry}} \right] = \underbrace{Q_{NO_x,dry} [ppmv_{dry}]}_{\text{measured}} \cdot \underbrace{\left(\frac{x_{O_2,Ox} - y_{O_2,dry,ref}}{x_{O_2,Ox} - y_{O_2,dry,M}} \right)}_{\text{Convert to ref. O}_2} \cdot \underbrace{\rho_{NO_2}}_{\text{Convert ppm in mg}}$$

NO_x emissions per kWh

$$Q_{NO_x} \left[\frac{mg}{kWh} \right] = \underbrace{Q_{NO_x,dry} [ppmv_{dry}]}_{\text{measured}} \cdot \underbrace{\rho_{NO_2}}_{\text{Convert ppm in mg}} \cdot \underbrace{\left(\frac{x_{O_2,ox}}{x_{O_2,ox} - y_{O_2,dry,M}} \right)}_{\frac{V_{tot,dry}}{V_{og,dry,min}}} \cdot \underbrace{\frac{v_{og,dry,min}}{H_i}}_{\text{Convert m}^3 \text{ in kWh}}$$

Oxygen balance:

$$V_{fa} \cdot x_{O_2,fa} + V_{og,(\lambda-1)} \cdot x_{O_2,ox} = V_{tot,dry} \cdot y_{O_2,dry,M}$$

$$V_{fa} \cdot x_{O_2,fa} + V_{og,(\lambda-1)} \cdot x_{O_2,ox} + V_{og,dry,min} \cdot x_{O_2,ox} - V_{og,dry,min} \cdot x_{O_2,ox} = V_{tot,dry} \cdot y_{O_2,dry,M}$$

$$x_{O_2,ox} (V_{fa} + V_{og,(\lambda-1)} + V_{og,dry,min}) - V_{og,dry,min} \cdot x_{O_2,ox} = V_{tot,dry} \cdot y_{O_2,dry,M}$$

$$\frac{V_{tot,dry}}{V_{og,dry,min}} = \frac{x_{O_2,ox}}{x_{O_2,ox} - y_{O_2,dry,M}}$$

NO_x emissions per kWh (new)

$$Q_{NOx} \left[\frac{mg}{kWh} \right] = \underbrace{Q_{NOx,dry} [ppmv_{dry}]}_{\text{measured}} \cdot \underbrace{\rho_{NO2}}_{\text{Convert ppm in mg}} \cdot \underbrace{\left(\frac{x_{O2,dry,\lambda} - x_{fa}}{y_{O2,dry,M} - x_{fa}} \right)}_{\text{Oxygen balance: } \frac{V_{og,dry,\lambda}}{V_{og,tot,dry}}} \cdot \underbrace{\frac{v_{og,dry,\lambda}}{H_i}}_{\text{Convert m}^3 \text{ in kWh}}$$

Oxygen balance:

$$x_{O2,fa} \cdot V_{fa} + x_{O2,dry,\lambda} \cdot V_{og,dry,\lambda} = y_{O2,dry,M} \cdot V_{og,tot,dry}$$

$$V_{fa} = V_{og,tot,dry} - V_{og,dry,\lambda}$$

$$\frac{V_{og,dry,\lambda}}{V_{og,tot,dry}} = \frac{x_{O2,dry,\lambda} - x_{O2,fa}}{y_{O2,dry,M} - x_{O2,fa}}$$

Cooling and Dilution Unit

